

Table S2: Probability of false alarms (PF) and probability of detection (PD) for the Open-source Java systems' experiment

PSI ↓	Target	Source	PD ↑	PF ↓	KS-test (shift)	PSI	Multi-Source	PD ↑	PF ↓	KS-test(shift)
0.001	ant-1.7	camel-1.6	0.778	0.463	No	0.001	ant-1.7 → all	0.798	0.426	No
0.012	ant-1.7	ivy-2.0	0.737	0.462	No					
0.002	ant-1.7	jedit-4.1	0.744	0.436	No					
0.092	ant-1.7	lucene-2.4	0.733	0.468	Yes					
0.051	ant-1.7	poi-3.0	0.733	0.462	Yes					
0.001	camel-1.6	ant-1.7	0.817	0.445	Yes	0.064	camel-1.6 → all	0.788	0.512	Yes
0.031	camel-1.6	ivy-2.0	0.751	0.542	Yes					
0.012	camel-1.6	jedit-4.1	0.748	0.55	Yes					
0.061	camel-1.6	lucene-2.4	0.747	0.551	Yes					
0.021	camel-1.6	poi-3.0	0.747	0.551	Yes					
0.012	ivy-2.0	ant-1.7	0.898	0.359	No	0.015	ivy-2.0 → all	0.769	0.456	Yes
0.031	ivy-2.0	camel-1.6	0.875	0.404	Yes					
0.013	ivy-2.0	jedit-4.1	0.866	0.465	Yes					
0.034	ivy-2.0	lucene-2.4	0.875	0.404	Yes					
0.048	ivy-2.0	poi-3.0	0.872	0.418	Yes					
0.002	jedit-4.1	ant-1.7	0.796	0.386	Yes	0.012	jedit-4.1 → all	0.689	0.502	No
0.012	jedit-4.1	camel-1.6	0.721	0.486	No					
0.013	jedit-4.1	ivy-2.0	0.696	0.424	Yes					
0.014	jedit-4.1	lucene-2.4	0.642	0.49	Yes					
0.022	jedit-4.1	poi-3.0	0.689	0.494	Yes					
0.092	lucene-2.4	ant-1.7	0.512	0.468	Yes	0.036	lucene-2.4 → all	0.521	0.451	No
0.061	lucene-2.4	camel-1.6	0.506	0.467	Yes					
0.034	lucene-2.4	ivy-2.0	0.497	0.48	Yes					
0.014	lucene-2.4	jedit-4.1	0.497	0.483	Yes					
0.001	lucene-2.4	poi-3.0	0.544	0.411	No					
0.051	poi-3.0	ant-1.7	0.534	0.47	Yes	0.0464	poi-3.0 → all	0.410	0.461	Yes
0.021	poi-3.0	camel-1.6	0.534	0.47	Yes					
0.048	poi-3.0	ivy-2.0	0.541	0.464	Yes					
0.022	poi-3.0	jedit-4.1	0.543	0.462	Yes					
0.001	poi-3.0	lucene-2.4	0.643	0.363	No					